

What have we learnt from models

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Outline

→ dark matter based galaxy formation models

Masses and SFRs

→ Low mass galaxies (10^9 - $10^{10}M_{\odot}$)
why is SF inefficient (w.r.t. halo accretion rates) but extends to $z=0$?
SN feedback

→ High mass galaxies ($>10^{11}M_{\odot}$)
why are they quenched early: accretion onto haloes? cooling?
heating source (AGN)

Basic principle of SAMs: Gravity

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Content of the Universe known to a few percent!!!

We have a working model of the universe in which 85% of matter only interacts through gravity

Before Planck

After Planck

Component	Before Planck (%)	After Planck (%)
Dark Energy	72.8%	68.3%
Dark Matter	22.7%	26.8%
Ordinary Matter	4.5%	4.9%

Evolution of structures is “fully known”

masses, sizes, temperatures, positions and velocities of dark matter haloes are “known”

Accretion

baryonic mass is given by cosmology:

$$M_b = f_b \times M_{DM}$$

Cooling

What happens to the baryons? hot atmosphere vs rapid cooling

MCMC

Henriques, Thomas, Oliver & Rosebooml. (2009),
 Henriques & Thomas (2010), Henriques et al. (2013), Henriques et al. (2015)

Comprehensive view on galaxy evolution

What processes shape the evolution of masses and SFRs of galaxies, of low and high mass, across cosmic time

low-mass galaxies:

what explains the strong evolution at $z < 2$ when accretion rates onto haloes are de-accelerating?

Accretion and Cooling

GALAXY FORMATION THROUGH HIERARCHICAL CLUSTERING

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ABSTRACT

We develop analytic methods for studying the formation of galaxies by gas condensation within massive dark halos. Our scheme applies to cosmogonies where structure grows through hierarchical clustering of a mixture of gas and dissipationless dark matter. It is an elaboration of the ideas of White & Rees. We adopt the simplest models consistent with our current understanding of N -body work on dissipationless clustering, and of numerical and analytic work on gas evolution and cooling. We also employ standard models for the evolution of stellar populations, and construct new models for the way star formation heats and enriches the surrounding gas. Although our approach is phenomenological, we avoid assumptions which have no clear physical basis. Our methods allow us to predict star formation as a function of location and time, and so the following properties of the galaxy population: current star formation rates and halo X-ray luminosities; current luminosity functions both for galaxies and for virialized systems; relations between present luminosity, circular velocity, metallicity, and stellar or total M/L ratio; the history of the OB star contribution to the metagalactic ionizing flux; and the distribution of faint blue (star-forming) galaxies in both apparent magnitude and redshift. In this paper we give detailed results only for a cold dark matter universe with $\Omega = 1$ and $H_0 = 50 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, although our methods are easily applied to other models. Even for this case, predictions depend strongly on the mean baryon density, on the fluctuation amplitude, on the models for heating and metal enrichment by massive stars, and on the initial mass function with which stars form. Our most successful models require a large baryon fraction ($\Omega_b/\Omega \gtrsim 0.1$) and efficient heating and enrichment of halo gas. They then approximately reproduce the characteristic luminosities of galaxies and of galaxy clusters, the observed relations between galaxy properties, and the kind of bias needed to reconcile $\Omega = 1$ with the

observed kinematics of galaxy clustering. However, the amplitude of this bias is too small, and additional sources of bias must be invoked. Our luminosity functions contain significantly more faint galaxies than are observed. This is a serious discrepancy which may be alleviated by starbursts in dwarf galaxies, by selective merging of such systems, and by observational selection against low surface brightness dwarfs. Successful

Subject headings: galaxies: clustering — galaxies: formation — galaxies:

The underlying distribution of dark matter is determinant.

The most important problems in galaxy formation can be identified in a model just with accretion and cooling

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EAGLE
Schaye 2015

MUFASA
Dave 2016

Figure 2. The galaxy stellar mass function at the redshifts shown in the upper left of each panel for simulation Ref-L100N1504 and Recal-L025N0752, in blue and green respectively. When the stellar mass falls below the mass of 100 baryonic particles curves are dotted, when there are fewer than 10 galaxies in a stellar mass bin curves are dashed. The redshift 0.1 GSMF is reproduced in each panel as a light blue curve, to highlight the evolution. Comparing Ref-L100N1504 to Recal-L025N0752, the simulations show good convergence over the redshift range shown, where there are more than 10 galaxies per bin. The data points show observations as indicated in the legends. Where necessary, observational data have been converted to a Chabrier IMF and Planck cosmology. The black points represent the observational redshift bin below the simulation redshift, while the grey curves are from the redshift bin above the simulation snapshot. Within the expected mass errors we find good agreement with observations of the GSMF from redshift 0 to 7. Between redshifts two and four the model tends to underestimate the masses of the brightest galaxies by around 0.2 dex, but these are very sensitive to the stellar mass errors in the observations, see text for discussion.

L-Galaxies
Henriques 2015

Gas Reincorporation

longer reincorporation time-scales for gas ejected by SN in low mass galaxies
 lower number density at early times, stronger build up at later times

$$t_{\text{reinc}} = -\gamma' \frac{10^{10} M_{\odot}}{M_{\text{vir}}},$$

Henriques et al. 2013
 in agreement with
 Oppenheimer & Dave
 2008

hydro should correctly
 follow the gas flows

Impact of Henriques13/15 Reincorporation

galaxy with $M_* \sim 10^9 M_\odot$ at $z=2$ in old model

Summary about low mass end

- dark matter and gravity are the backbone of galaxy formation
- significant inefficiency of cooling is necessary to explain the mass function of low mass objects: decouple accretion rate onto halos from accretion rate onto galaxies
- we tried a lot of processes over the years, but SN feedback seems to be the only one energetic enough to do the job

Properties of Massive Galaxies

More than 50% of the stellar mass density at $z=0$ is in quenched galaxies

at $z=2$, 50% of the massive galaxies are already quenched

Fig 6: The red fraction in SDSS as functions of stellar mass and environment.

Faster evolution

Denser regions always accrete more material so there is always more mass in massive haloes

However, when normalised over the mass at $z=0$, high-mass haloes are the later to accrete their mass

unlike massive galaxies

What Causes Quenching?

- Is quenching caused by the reduction of accretion rates onto haloes?
- Is shock (gravitational) heating, and the longer cooling times in haloes with $M_{\text{vir}} > 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$, enough?
- Can the velocity dispersion provide sufficient pressure support, preventing the cold gas from collapsing and leading to morphological quenching?
- Do we need an additional heating source?

Must be tightly connected to stellar mass!

Properties of Massive Galaxies

what is needed:

1. the right number of low mass galaxies
2. the right number of massive galaxies
3. quenched massive galaxies (all of them!)

→ SN feedback can produce the right number of massive galaxies but:
too few low mass and massive galaxies not quenched

→ Quenching might naturally happen if all the low entropy gas cools and forms stars but:
too many massive galaxies

Slower Accretion Rates

the slower dark matter accretion rates at late times cannot explain the properties of massive galaxies

Why quicker drop in SFR for massive galaxies?

Saying that massive galaxies evolve faster is not an explanation. Why stellar growth different from the halo growth?

Shock Heating (longer cooling times $> 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$)

High velocity gas is shock heated during collapse. Subsequent cooling times are longer for high mass haloes

Fig. 8.7. Same as Fig.8.1, except that now we also indicate Λ_{crit} for halos in the redshift range $0 \leq z \leq 3$ (shaded area). Halos with $\Lambda > \Lambda_{\text{crit}}$ accrete their gas in the cold mode, while those with $\Lambda < \Lambda_{\text{crit}}$ experience hot mode accretion.

White & Frenk 1991, Birnboim & Dekel (2003), Keres et al. (2004)

Shock Heating (longer cooling times $> 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$)

Although it seems that inefficient cooling could be enough, there is much more mass to cool at high masses due to the efficient cooling in lower masses

Morphological Quenching

velocity dispersion provides pressure support against the gravitational collapse of cold gas: there is cold gas, but it isn't forming stars

10% increase in M_* if all gas turned into stars

In Massive haloes all the gas is hot, why?

AGN (or other heating source)

AGN feedback ensures that gas remains hot in massive haloes and there is no cold gas to fuel star formation

The Stellar Mass Function

AGN feedback produces the break on the stellar mass function that is kept constant with time - “at the right halo mass”

Quenching

passive fraction vs stellar mass

quenching efficiencies

passive fraction vs halo mass

Henriques et al. 2016

SFRD

Without feedback, there is a drop at late times, but not enough
SN feedback suppresses SF at all times and AGN at late times
SN is less effective at $z < 2$ because SF happens in more massive objects
The drop below $z=2$ “requires AGN feedback”

Summary about low mass end

- dark matter and gravity are the backbone of galaxy formation
- significant inefficiency of cooling is necessary to explain the mass function of low mass objects: decouple accretion rate onto halos from accretion rate onto galaxies - SN feedback
- In order to understand the properties of massive galaxies we need: 1) the right number of low mass galaxies, 2) the right number of massive galaxies, 3) quenched massive galaxies (all of them!)
- Slow accretion rates, longer cooling times, morphological quenching, all go in the right directions but are not enough to explain quenching.
- We need an heating source, and AGN is sufficient